

ROMANIAN ENERGETIC SECURITY - A DIMENSION OF THE NATIONAL SECURITY

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Abstract

This paper aims to analyzing the Romania's energy security, both, overall and specific in terms of recent developments. The purpose of this paper is to stress the fact that energy security, both globally and in Romania, is one of the cornerstones for individual and nation's security.

The paper postulates that at the national level, economic security is facing major threats that intertwine and influence each other: black economy, corruption and organized crime. In the economic dimension of security we may distinguish also various types of threats to the basic values and specific issues, such as energy security or critical infrastructure security, which are currently high on the security agenda for most states.

The importance of energy security in the complex of security threats is highlighted in the National Defense Strategy for 2015-2019. The strategy emphasizes the importance of a strong energetic sector in Romania related to Europe and also to the world energy situation,, into the chapter entitled "The economic and energetic dimension". According to this document, energetic security is carried out by operational adapting and optimizing the structure of the consumption of primary energy resources, increasing energy efficiency, developing projects aimed to ensure diversification of the resources acces, increasing the interconnection capacity and competitiveness, including through implementing the objectives of the Energy Union.

Keywords: insurance of energetic security, economic dimension of the security, energetic resources, Romanian energetic strategy

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Introduction

The best known definition of energy security is provided by the International Energy Agency: "Energy security is uninterrupted access to affordable energy sources" (**International Energy Agency, 2015, Energy Security**) This definition is criticized, however, by the researchers from academia and leaders of the main producing countries. For example, for energy-producing countries like Russia, energy security is uninterrupted access to markets (**Yenikieff, 2006**). This issue was discussed at the G8 summit organized in 2006 in St. Petersburg, where it was deemed that energy security may be achieved by increasing transparency and predictability of markets, improving the present investment climate in the energy sector, energy diversification, security of critical physical infrastructure for energy (**Global Energy Security St Petersburg, 2006**). Therefore, with changes happened in the international system, definition of energy security expands to include the idea of ensuring the integrity of the whole energy chain (extraction/production, distribution, transport) and its associated essential infrastructure (**Yergin, 2006, 78**).

The components of the concept of energy security are closely linked to the energy chain stages. In each stage of the chain, the goal is the same, i.e. making the process seamless and relatively inexpensive, but the risks / ways / means to combat them are specific. Risks may arise at each stage and may be caused by various factors, natural and human.

For countries that import energy, a greater risk is the unstable price developments. The price of a barrel of oil went from \$ 55.12 in January 2006 to \$ 137.11 in July 2008, returning then to \$ 75.55 in 2010 (**Băhnăreanu, 2008, 15**). Also a risk to importing countries is the political pressure from exporting states, which may refuse export waiting for higher prices. The best known example in recent years is the Russian-Ukrainian dispute over gas supplies (especially those of 2006, 2009, 2014), when Russia suspended gas deliveries to Ukraine, based on commercial and political reasons.

Many high risks may arise when energy transport is done, because accidents, terrorist activities or piracy may put serious threat. In recent years, many cases of piracy took place around the Horn of Africa, encouraged by the lack of a stable government in Somalia. Only vigorous military action by the international community, both at sea and in Somalia, has reduced the number of such attacks. Also, theft of oil or electricity may pose a risk caused by human factors, risk that occurred in Romania in the past and happens nowadays. As examples of natural risk in the stage of power transmission one may mention the devastating effect of hurricanes Katrina and Rita on the US energy transport infrastructure (**Yergin, 2006, 70**). A relatively new vulnerability appears in the electricity transmission (also in oil and gas pipelines), with the deployment of "smart grid" through the integration of information technology in traditional networks. "Smart Grid" is vulnerable to cyber attacks, software malfunctions and may represent a significant problem, causing a power failure in the northwestern US and southwestern Canada in 2003 (**Dan Verton, 2003**).

To meet these challenges, Member States may adopt a number of strategies. The most important thing is to diversify energy sources, refining and distribution capabilities, as recommended by Winston Churchill ninety years ago. Another approach is to create energy stocks, e.g. US strategic oil reserves of about 727 million barrels are stored in underground

tanks (**The Strategic Petroleum Reserve**). Full integration of markets to free them from political control and the creation of institutions that facilitates information exchange in this area represent another way to avoid geopolitical battles for control of resources (**Yergin, 2006, 76**). Also providing the safety of transport infrastructure against terrorist either classic or cyber attacks is necessary. Electrical "Smart Grid" transport infrastructure of the US has been the target of some attacks, which, however, did not cause significant damage (**Siobhan Gorman, 2009**).

The concept of "energy security" is still relatively new, being increasingly developed by the state authorities in the recent years, given the new threats and events on the international stage. Moreover, proving its importance, the concept has made its way to Romania's National Security Strategy of 2007 and to the content of 2010 National Defense Strategy where it is stipulated that "*Energy security has returned to the state attention among the main elements of concern, considering the implications for the members of society both to their security and their prosperity*" (**Strategia Națională de Apărare, 2010, 7**).

The importance of energy security within the complex security threats is emphasized in the country's national defense strategy for the period 2015-2019 which is intended to provide a strong Romania's role in Europe and in the world and contains a chapter entitled "economic and energy". According to this document, "energy security is achieved by adapting and optimizing operational structure of consumption of primary energy resources, increasing energy efficiency, developing projects to ensure diversification of access to resources, increase the interconnection capacity and competitiveness, including through implementation of the Energy Union's objectives" (**Strategia de Apărare Națională a Țării pentru perioada 2015-2019**).

The overall objective of the energy sector strategy is to ensure conditions for its energy needs on the medium and long term, affordable, suitable for a modern market economy and a civilized standard of living in terms of quality, security of supply, respecting principles of sustainable development (**Strategia energetică a României pentru perioada 2007-2020, actualizată pentru perioada 2011-2020**).

Romania has a wide range of resources, but a reduced amount of primary energy fossil resources and also minerals: oil, natural gas, coal and uranium, but compensatory holds an important stock of potentially usable renewable resources (**Strategia energetică a României pentru perioada 2007-2020, actualizată pentru perioada 2011-2020**).

1. Guidelines to EU energy security. Case study: Romania

At EU level, the fundamental energy objectives are established according to the provisions of the Lisbon Treaty, which entered into force on December, the 1 st., 2009. The treaty stipulates that the European Union's targets aim to achieve the functioning of the energy market, security of energy sources in the Union, promoting energy efficiency and the development of new and renewable sources and promoting the interconnection of markets (**Băhnăreanu, 2010, 17**). Before the entry into force of the Lisbon Treaty, the European Commission adopted a series of ambitious targets for EU energy policy, called the simplified formula of 20-20-20 (reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 20% and increase by the same percentage the use of renewable energy and also the energy efficiency at EU level) (**An energy**

policy for Europe, 2007), the deadline for their completion being the year 2020. In 2010, the European Commission found out that the means to achieve those goals need to be amended (**Energy 2020 A Strategy for competitive, sustainable and secure energy, 2010**). Launching 2030 Energy Strategy by European Union in 2014 confirmed the extension of energy targets to the year 2030, by setting more ambitious goals (40% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and increasing to 27% the energy produced from renewable sources and also the energy savings) (**2030 climate and energy goals for a competitive, secure and low-carbon EU economy, 2014**).

The principal means by which it seeks to achieve the objectives set at European level one may mention: reducing the energy consumption in the EU by 20% by 2020, ensuring an integrated European energy mix by liberalizing domestic markets to allow free competition between energy suppliers, offering cheap and safe energy for the end users, obtaining and strengthening Europe's leadership in energy technology and innovation, and establishing strong partnerships with external countries, particularly with EU neighbors.

In terms of the relationship with Russia, which is the most important partner of EU in energy (36% of gas imports and 31% of oil imports EU come from Russia) (**Energy from abroad, EU-Russia Energy Relations**), one may conclude that it is necessary to learn from bilateral disputes since 2009, disputes which have led to cutting gas supply for a short period which strongly affected some Member States of EU (**Russian gas reaches Europe again, 2009**). On 22 March 2013 it was signed in Moscow a "roadmap for energy cooperation between EU and Russia until 2050", which postulates the energy interdependence between EU and Russia and recommends some measures such as frequent exchanges of information, measures for opening the markets to Russian companies in Europe and for European companies in Russia and ensuring minimum levels of deliveries of Russian gas to EU countries (**EU-Russia Energy Cooperation until 2050, 2013**).

The main objective established by Romania's energy strategy is " providing energy needs both now and in the medium and long term, at a price as low as suitable for a modern market economy and also a civilized standard of living under the conditions of a good quality and reliability for energy utilities, ensuring the food safety, and in accordance with the principles of sustainable development" (**Strategia energetică, 5**). Also, the Romanian Energy Strategy refers to the EU's energy strategy, underlining the legislation to be adopted for implementing the pollution standards and targets 20-20-20, focusing on the fact that Romania has assumed for the year 2020 the target of 24% (i.e. over EU standards) of energy that must be produced from renewable sources (**Strategia energetică a României, 9**).

The paper considers a number of factors, which are both advantages and disadvantages for our country, for establishing a series of measures, which are expected to lead to energy security. Among the competitive advantages one may include hydroelectric potential which ensures less dependence than the European average on imported energy resources; complex and diversified transport infrastructure, a positive perception for the program of nuclear power production, upgrading the institutional and legislative framework, relatively high ability to interconnect electricity transmission and natural gas pipelines from neighboring countries with similar systems (**Strategia energetică a României, 28**). Among the disadvantages and risks,

the strategy states: non-compliance with EU emission standards for air pollutants by a large proportion of electricity producing units, requiring significant funding for aligning our standards, the high cost of green field used for operating production and transport facilities which were closed overtime, the high costs and low efficiency of the transport infrastructure, the increased economic vulnerability of the population to higher energy prices imposed by European Commission for so called alignment to European energy prices, reduced capacity to cope with terrorist actions directed to energy production facilities and to transport systems, increased dependence on imports of primary energy imports (crude oil and natural gas) (**Strategia energetică a României, 31-32**).

Romania's energy strategy assumes that only coal may contribute to Romania's long-term energy security while oil and gas resources will be exhausted in the coming years. It is therefore necessary to replace them by other resources or to develop electricity production from renewable sources, or to increase the imports of exhaustible sources (oil, gas, uranium) (**Strategia energetică a României, 33**). The strategy also envisages that the high costs of obtaining energy from renewable sources will hamper providing the necessary energy in the context of the expected consumption growth. Thus, this document concludes that based on data analysis, the primary energy imports will increase in the near future. It observed that "the dependence on primary energy imports has increased in the last decade from 21.5% in 1999 to 27.2% in 2008, with a maximum of 31.9% in 2007" (**Strategia energetică a României, 17**).

Romania's energy strategy sets out a series of lines of actions, measures and scenarios that must be taken into consideration. These scenarios refer to the rate of economic growth and to the increase of energy consumption, estimating growth rates, however, different. Among the directions of actions and measures one may mention "effective management and rational and safe use of resources of depleted primary energy from Romania while maintaining an acceptable level of these resources (in terms of economic availability and security), the import of primary energy resources (dependence on limited / controlled sources)", increasing the energy efficiency, improving the competitiveness of Romanian companies, promoting the use of renewable energy resources, " pro-active participation in EU efforts to formulate an energy strategy for the whole Europe, following up and promoting the Romania's interests, diversifying the supply sources and developing safe alternative transport routes; participation in transcontinental hydrocarbons transport projects to Central Europe through potential Romanian routes" (**Strategia energetică a României, 34**).

2. Romania's prospects in the field of energy security

Romania's energy security may be analyzed in the current context, in terms of different components of this sector. Each component has different advantages and vulnerabilities that must be considered in the next period in order to achieve the objective of ensuring energy security. Electricity production in Romania is still using coal-based power plants and hydrocarbons, which are currently highly polluting, far exceeding European standards for pollutant emissions. A share of 52.2% of electricity production in 2009 was achieved in such plants and only 27.3% were provided by hydro plants and 20.5% by a nuclear plant (**Strategia energetică a României, 20**). This proportion has changed significantly in the last years, but in

a positive way, reaching to 40% in 2014 for fossil power plants (28% coal and 12% hydrocarbons), 28.5% for hydroelectric plants, 18% for hydroelectric power plant, 12.9% for other renewable energies (**Raport anual 2010**). Besides pollution, another weakness of the electricity generation system is the age of the machinery and equipment in the thermal power plants and their degree of wear and low efficiency, below the European average (**Strategia energetică a României, 21**).

On the other hand, Romania's electricity production has three main advantages. First, our country produces more electricity than it can consume. With the exception of 2012 (1402 GWh imported and 1149 GWh exported), Romania has been a net exporter of electric energy (**Agencia Națională de Reglementare a Energiei, Raport Anual 2012**). For example, in 2009, Romania exported about 3154 GWh and imported 676 GWh (**Agencia Națională de Reglementare a Energiei, Raport Anual 2009**). The second advantage is the existence of a electricity commodity market (OPCOM), flexible and modern (you can make contracts of 1MW unit, weekly, monthly, quarterly) (**Strategia energetică a României, 26**) in Bucharest, which creates a potential redirection of electricity which by its nature can not be stored. This, combined with interconnection with neighboring states, offers Romania the opportunity to become a regional leader in the field (**Niță, 2015**). Thirdly, Romania has rivers that may provide large water quantities for hydropower production, the most important source of renewable energy. Thus, Romania has achieved the target of 24% energy from renewable resources already in early January 2014, then limiting the subsidies for investment in this field, usually granted to wind, solar, biomass and microhydro plants.

According to the BP Statistical Review (2014), in 2013 the proved natural gas reserves of Romania were 100 billion cubic meters (4 times smaller than in 1993) and proved oil reserves amounted to 600 million barrels (half of 1993 level). Annual gas production is 11 billion cubic meters and gas consumption is 12.5 billion cubic meters. The oil production is 87,000 barrels daily, which means an annual production of 31.755 million barrels (4.35 million tons) while the daily consumption is 188,000 barrels, which means an annual consumption of 68.620 million barrels (9.4 million tons). As you may see, Romania produces less than it consumes and it is forced to import hydrocarbon resources. In percentage, the above data demonstrate that Romania oil imports have a share of 64.73% in oil consumption in Romania and 22% in natural gas consumption. These percentages highlight Romania's high dependence of hydrocarbon imported resources.

The decreasing rate of domestic hydrocarbon reserves is 10% per year, which means that in the absence of additional resources, dependence on gas and oil imports will significantly increase in the next years. National Statistics Institute issued on 01.14.2015 a press release showing the evolution of energy resources in the period 01.01.2014 - 30.11.2014 (provisional data). The data are presented in "tons of oil equivalent," but what interests us are the percentages that show the ratio between imported resources and consumption.

**Energy resources in 01.01.2014 - 11.30.2014 period
- provisional data (thousand of tons oil equivalent) –**

	Total consumption	Production	Import	Import share(%)
Total resources	29329,8	20073,5	9256,3	31,56
Meaning				
Net coal	4535,7	4093,5	442,2	9,75
Crude oil	9581,9	3473,8	6108,1	63,75
Natural gas	8296,6	7923,4	373,2	4,50
Hydropower and nuclear energy	4636	4582,8	53,2	1,15

Source: National Statistics Institute, 2014

In this context, one of the most disputed aspects of energy security, both in terms of energy and in geopolitical terms, is to supply Romania with hydrocarbons (oil and gas) with no risk of increasing its dependence on imports, in particular from the Russian Federation. The first way to avoid the increased import dependence is the diversification of energy resources and import sources. In the hydrocarbons field one may find two important options: gas and oil exploitation on the Black Sea shelf, especially along the marine coast, and/or shale gas (with a huge environmental impact). According to some estimates, these two resources combined could lead to the transformation of Romania from a net gas importer into a net gas exporter, bringing a contribution of 2% to our GDP (**Constantin, 2013**). The gas reserves in the Black Sea are estimated at 84 billion cubic meters, equivalent to the Romania's consumption for six years. Investments are high and operation of marine field may be very difficult due to the great depth and extraction costs. On the other hand, the potential exploitation of shale gas in the Vaslui County was strongly contested by civil society and the people of Pungesti due to unconventional methods of mining method (fracking) that may cause high pollution of groundwater or small earthquakes due to the injection pressure rock solution (**Dimulescu, 2013**).

Projects that may reduce the import dependence on Russia's gas, that could directly help Romania's position were abandoned or slowed (Nabucco and AGRI). The only projects that remain viable for Romania are PEO (Pan-European Oil Pipeline), a pipeline planned with a total length of 1360 km (including 649 km in Romania) which will start from the port of Constanta to the destination of Trieste, Italy and interconnection strategy based on the National Gas Transmission System for linking our transport system to the natural gas transportation systems in the neighboring countries, elaborated by Transgaz Medias SA, and providing some actions in the following areas:

- interconnection with Hungary based on the Arad-Szeged link (operational at this time on the direction of Szeged-Arad);
- interconnection with Bulgaria, based on Giurgiu-Ruse link ;
- interconnection with the Republic of Moldova, based on Ungheni-Iasi link;
- interconnection with Serbia (**MAE, Securitatea energetică**).

However, this solution may be a double-edged sword for Romania. Romania and the neighboring states are in a sensitive area in the neighborhood of Russia, but it has the lowest dependence on imported resources, at least in terms of natural gas, unlike Hungary and Bulgaria which are dependent on imported gas more than 80 %. But Romania has high potential energy resources that may reduce reliance on Russia resources and perhaps even may become a gas

supplier in South East Europe. Since Romania has a low share of the imported resources in its energy consumption (approximately 32%), but taking into account national interests our country would not have any interest to share its energy resources with neighboring countries. The only country for which the Romania may supply some energy resources and this deeply corresponds to the national interest is Moldova. However, Romania is involved in an European project for decreasing the import dependence on Russia's energy resources. Thus an interconnection with the neighboring countries like Bulgaria and Hungary, coincides with the national interest but it does not reduce the dependence on Russia's imports. Only a full pipeline interconnection in all Europe may provide good alternatives to Russian gas.

Regarding the electricity field, where imports had a small share (1%), Romania is almost energy independent. In this respect, Romania intends the construction of a hydro-power plants at Lăpușești Tarnița, Cluj county, with a settled output of 1,000 MWh and an estimated annual production of 1.64 TWh, and the construction of last two reactors at Cernavoda nuclear plant (the two new nuclear reactors will use CANDU 6 technology and will enter into commercial operation in 2024). The project aims to achieve a competitive electricity production and counteract supply shortfalls that will occur after 2020, also to increase the importance of electricity for ensuring energy independence and reduce the dependence on imports, both for Romania and for other Member States already looking for solutions to reduce imports of energy resources. Taking into account the European standards and the need for a higher security of its own energy system, one must ensure viable alternatives for a stable production, for meeting environmental requirements and, very important, for ensuring fair prices to the final consumer" (Lulache, 2014).

Conclusions

Energy security is becoming an increased component of economic security. The serious analysis of energy security involves the investigation of vulnerabilities, dangers, threats and risks. Romania may become an energy independent country. For this reason, energy security is a key area of national security, as emphasized in the National Defence Strategy of Romania. It is therefore vital to reduce the dependency on those who, at the first glance, have a monopoly in terms of energy and power (Russia). This may be achieved through international cooperation and by coagulating similar interests that dictate the actions of the security environment. It is important to understand that interdependence, not dependence, is the key for achieving the energy security on a large scale and for supporting a sustainable and rapid economic development.

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